

RESOLUTE
Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

Project number 777372

**WP3 – Development of
 quantitative transport assays**

D3.1 Assays for (electrogenic) transporters

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Publishable Summary

The aim of WP3 is to develop quantitative transport assays for more than 50% of the SLC family. This can be achieved by a consortium-wide effort, combining the functional and deorphanisation data/hypotheses generated in WP1 and WP2 with know-how and technologies available to the industrial partners and the Academic Expert Laboratories. Together with well-established approaches, innovative ones are used to assess SLC functionality.

Task 3.1 is specifically focused on setting assays for transporters predicted or known to be electrogenic upon the use of voltage-sensing dyes, in the miniaturized format of 384 MTP. Extrapolating from the percentage of known electrogenic transporters in the genome, we expect about 40-45% of SLCs to have such properties, and to be located at the cell surface. This SLC subset should therefore be amenable to be analysed in cell-based assays that measure membrane potential changes, using fluorescent dyes, including membrane-potential, calcium, and sodium-dyes.

Important prerequisite for the assay set up is the availability of a natural or surrogate SLC substrate/activator, which can be retrieved either by published data or identified in the deorphaning processes carried out in WP2. WP1 generated many HEK293 JumpIn T-REx -SLC overexpressing cell lines and for most of them immunofluorescent data, showing the plasma membrane localization of the SLC, were also available.

The functionality of 29 different cell lines, by using fluorescent dyes and different substrates, was tested and we got a positive outcome for more than 50% of them. We can therefore assess that the use of fluorescent dyes, represents a useful approach to analyze the functionality of electrogenic SLCs, and to determine the affinity of their substrates and blockers, in a miniaturized format, amenable to High Throughput Screening purposes.

A particular case for the use of fluorescent dyes is the determination of influx of Cd²⁺ (cadmium ion), a surrogate substrate for Zn²⁺ (zinc ion) transporters of the SLC30 and SLC39 families. We developed a prototype assay for SLC39A8, and we expect this approach to be widely applicable for members of the Zn²⁺ transporter families. This broader application will be initiated early in 2021.

Beside analyzing electrogenic SLCs, we also tested the functionality of SLCs, which are activated by substrates, which are known to be also ligands for GPCRs. We analyzed 4 different SLCs. We used an impedance-based technology (xCELLigence) to demonstrate the functionality of these SLCs in cells that express a cognate G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) which is activated by the same substrate as the SLC, or via a different mechanism. We prove functionality for all 4 tested SLCs and demonstrate pharmacological inhibition, indicating that the impedance-based assay is a suitable alternative to assess SLC function.

Methods

The criteria for selecting the SLC-OE cell lines to be tested with **voltage sensitive dyes** was based on three different parameters:

- Potential electrogenicity
- Plasma membrane localization
- Presence of a known or predicted substrate

Upon receipt of both the SLC-OE and WT JumpIN cell lines, the following workflow was applied:

- Cells were seeded in 384-well plates, at a density of 10.000 c/w, and at the same time they were induced, or not induced, with 1µg/mL Doxycycline
- Up to 3 different substrates were tested at 8 concentrations in quadruplicates
- Up to two different fluorescent dyes were used, and in specific case, transient transfection of genetically encoded biosensors was performed
- Where needed, different extracellular buffer conditions were tested

An SLC was judged as *validated* when:

- the fluorescent response signal detected in the HEK293 JumpIn T-REx OE cell line treated with Doxycycline was in line with the expected electrogenic transport
- the fluorescent response signal is substrate dose/dependent and significantly differs from the response of the not-induced HEK293 JumpIn T-REx OE cell line and of the HEK293 JumpIn T-REx WT cell line (induced and not-induced)

Below are reported the details of the readout systems used and of the experimental protocols applied.

Fluorescent dyes are non-protein molecules that allow to measure ion currents not directly but monitoring changes in fluorescent signals. Among these are the Membrane Potential Dye, which can detect changes in the membrane potential, thus allowing the characterization of electrogenic transporters. In addition, ion sensitive dyes are available, and can detect changes in the concentration of a specific ion, such as Calcium.

FLIPR Membrane Potential dye is a lipophilic, anionic, bis-oxonol dye from Molecular Devices, able to cross the plasma membrane and to measure voltage changes by its potential-dependent accumulation and redistribution. When the cells are depolarized, the dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye efflux and decreased fluorescence, as reported in the figure below:

A general protocol for the use of MP dye requires to discard cell medium and load the cells with the dye in a suitable buffer for a period that typically ranges from 15 to 30 minutes, at Room Temperature (RT).

Ca²⁺ measurement is critical for numerous biological investigations. Fluorescent probes that show spectral responses upon binding of Ca²⁺ have enabled researchers to investigate changes in intracellular free Ca²⁺ concentrations. There are several calcium-sensitive dyes available, with different calcium affinities and different excitation/emission spectra. Among these, Screen Quest Fluo-8 NW Calcium dye is the brightest calcium indicator available, providing a homogeneous fluorescence-based assay for detecting the intracellular calcium mobilization. Cells are pre-loaded with Fluo-8 NW (which can cross cell membrane), dissolved in the proper buffer. Typically, cells are incubated with the dye for 1h at RT. Once inside the cell, the lipophilic blocking groups of Fluo-8 AM are cleaved by non-specific cell esterase, resulting in a negatively charged fluorescent dye that stays inside cells, and its fluorescence is greatly enhanced upon binding to calcium.

Detection of fluorescent indicator dyes is achieved by means of a fluorescent plate reader (such as FLIPR^{TETRA} or Hamamatsu FDSS) able to excite the probe and to acquire its emission. This instrumentation together with the characteristics of the dyes enable the high throughput of the assay. Typically, for Fluo-8 NW and MP dye experiments, cells are excited at the plate reader using λ_{exc} 470 - 495 nm / λ_{em} 515 - 575 nm filters, and a λ_{exc} 510-545 nm / λ_{em} 565 - 625 nm filters, respectively.

For detection of **Cd²⁺ influx, the calcium-5 dye** from Molecular Devices was employed. The same settings for excitation/emission were used as described above.

The main advantages in using the abovementioned fluorescent dyes is that most of them are very easy to load and require a single incubation step without washing the cell monolayer, which results in a rapid and high throughput assay. In addition, these assays are flexible and have low temporal resolution, given the fast response of the dye. Nevertheless, the main limitation in the use of fluorescent dyes is that a cell loading step is required, with the consequent risk of affecting the cell physiology.

The criteria for selecting the SLC-OE cell lines to be tested with **the impedance-based technology** is based on the evidence that a transporter shares its substrate (e.g., adenosine, dopamine) with a G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR). The SLC needs to be expressed in live cells together with a cognate GPCR. Uptake of substrate by the transporter decreases its local extracellular concentration, thereby limiting the ability of the substrate to activate the GPCR. Conversely, pharmacological inhibition of the transporter augments the substrate induced GPCR response, providing an assay window for identification of transporter modulators. The assays were developed in 96-well plate format, using an impedance-based biosensor, xCELLigence.

Results

The table below summarizes the results obtained:

Contributor	SLC	Electrogenic	Read-out	Substrate (EC50)	Inhibitor tested	Outcome
AXXAM	SLC7A3	YES	MP dye	L-Orn (237 μ M), L-Arg (283 μ M), L-Lys (158 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC6A5*	YES	MP dye	Glycine (co-transport with Na+) (128 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC5A7	YES	MP dye	Choline (co-transport with Na+) (17 μ M)	YES (HC-3)	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC5A4*	YES	MP dye	Glucose (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC5A2	YES	MP dye	Glucose (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC34A1	YES	MP dye	Na ₂ HPO ₄ , KH ₂ PO ₄ (co-transport with Na+) (32 μ M; 39 μ M)	YES (LC-1)	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC24A4	YES	Ca ²⁺ dye (Fluo-8 NW)	Na ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , K ⁺ (KCl: 174 mM)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC24A2	YES	Ca ²⁺ dye (Fluo-8 NW)	Na ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , K ⁺ (KCl: 280 mM)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC1A7	YES	MP dye	L-Glu, L-Asp, L-Pro (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC1A6	YES	MP dye	L-Glu, L-Asp, L-Cys (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC1A3	YES	MP dye	L-Glu, L-Asp, L-Cys (co-transport with Na+) (16 μ M; 15 μ M; 376 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC1A1	YES	MP dye	L-Glu, L-Asp, L-Cys (co-transport with Na+) (L-Cys: 161 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC18A2	YES	FFN206	Fluorescent substrate (FFN206) (2 μ M); vesicular localization	YES (TBZ, Reserpine)	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC18A1	YES	FFN206	Fluorescent substrate (FFN206) (2 μ M); vesicular localization	YES (Reserpine)	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC17A3	YES	MP dye	Polyspecific organic anions (PAH, uric acid)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC17A1	YES	MP dye	Polyspecific organic anions (PAH, uric acid)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC13A4	YES	MP dye	Sulfates (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED

AXXAM	SLC13A3	YES	MP dye	α -ketoglutaric acid, succinic acid (co-transport with Na+) (54 μ M; 107 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC13A1	YES	MP dye	Sulfates (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC11A1	YES	Calcein-AM dye	Mn ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ (intracellular localization)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC10A1*	YES	MP dye	Bile acids (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC23A1	YES	MP dye	L-Ascorbic Acid (co-transport with Na+) (156 μ M)	YES (Phloretin)	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC45A1	YES	MP dye	Glucose, Sucrose (co-transport with H+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC34A2	YES	MP dye	Inorganic phosphate (co-transport with Na+)	NO	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC5A11	YES	MP dye	Myo-inositol (co-transport with Na+) (104 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC15A2	YES	MP dye	Gly-Sar, L-Carnosine (co-transport with H+) (39 μ M; 28 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC6A6	YES	MP dye	Na ⁺ /Cl ⁻ Taurine/GABA transporter (10 μ M; 354 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC6A9	YES	MP dye	Na ⁺ /Cl ⁻ Glycine transporter (106 μ M)	YES (ALX5407)	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC6A12	YES	MP dye	Na ⁺ /Cl ⁻ Betaine/GABA transporter (GABA: 36 μ M)	NO	VALIDATED
NOVARTIS	SLC38A9	NO	Ca ²⁺ dye	CdCl ₂	YES (tool compound)	VALIDATED
ULEI	SLC29A1	NO	Impedance	Adenosine	NBTI	VALIDATED
ULEI	SLC6A2	YES	Impedance	Norepinephrine, Dopamine, Epinephrine	Nisoxetine	VALIDATED
ULEI	SLC6A3	YES	Impedance	Dopamine	GBR12909	VALIDATED
ULEI	SLC1A3	YES	Impedance	Glutamate, Aspartate	TFB-TBOA	VALIDATED

* for the three indicated cell lines, a cross-contamination with other SLCs was detected and communicated to Axxam after that the cell line had already been tested. These cell lines were therefore discarded.

Below are reported the Dose-Response (D/R) curves, or kinetics, of the validated SLCs, obtained using the indicated read-outs.

For some of them, the kinetic fluorescent traces associated to the use of a specific inhibitor are also reported.

In all the experiments, the WT cell line (HEK293-JumpIn TReX, not overexpressing the transporter) was included as control. Both target over-expressing (OE) as well as WT cell lines were induced (Doxy-treated, 1µg/mL, 24h) as well as not-induced (not-treated). Typically, Doxycycline was added to the cells during the seeding procedure.

All the experiments were carried out using a miniaturized format, meaning that the cells were seeded and stimulated in 384-well plates (poly-Lysine coated), for the fluorescent dye-based tests and in 96-well plates for the xCELLigence technology.

SLC7A3

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). L-Arginine, L-Lysine and L-Ornithine were used as substrates. Typically, for the MP dye read-out, fluorescent data are reported as Area Under the Curve (AUC):

SLC5A7

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). Choline Chloride was used as substrate. The effect of the specific inhibitor HC-3 (10 μM) is also reported:

SLC34A1

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in Tyrode's buffer Na^+ free). Na_2HPO_4 and KH_2PO_4 were used as substrates. The results obtained injecting these substrates in a Na^+ -free condition are also shown, demonstrating that the transporter is not functional in the absence of Na^+ . The kinetic traces obtained when cells were pre-incubated with the specific inhibitor LC-1 (30 μM) are also indicated:

SLC24A2

Read out: **Fluo-8NW dye** (dissolved in buffer K⁺ free, containing 145 mM Na⁺ ± Ouabain 500 μM - an inhibitor of Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase). KCl (starting from 600 mM), dissolved in buffer K⁺ free / Na⁺ free (NMDG-Cl 145 mM was used to replace Na⁺) was used as substrate. These buffer conditions induced the reverse mode of action of the transporter. Typically, when Fluo-8 NW dye is used, fluorescent data are reported as Response over Baseline ($\Delta F/F_0$):

SLC24A4

Read out: **Fluo-8NW dye** (dissolved in buffer K⁺ free, containing 145 mM Na⁺ ± Ouabain 500 μM - an inhibitor of Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase). KCl (starting from 600 mM), dissolved in buffer K⁺ free / Na⁺ free (NMDG-Cl 145 mM was used to replace Na⁺) was used as substrate. These buffer conditions induced the reverse mode of action of the transporter:

SLC1A1

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). L-Cysteine, L-Glutamic Acid and L-Aspartic Acid were used as substrates. L-Glutamic Acid and L-Aspartic Acid induced a higher and specific fluorescent response in the target cell line, but lower concentrations of substrates should be tested to better fit the curve and calculate the EC₅₀ values:

SLC1A3

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). L-Cysteine, L-Glutamic Acid and L-Aspartic Acid were used as substrates:

SLC18A1

For this transporter, a known and well described fluorescent surrogate substrate was used: FFN206. A dose dependent FFN206 fluorescent increase was detected in the SLC18A1 induced condition only, showing EC₅₀ values of ~ 2 μM. Fluorescence was acquired at Pherastar FSX (exc: 360 nm; em: 450 nm). Fluorescence data are reported as RFU. The dose-response curve of the inhibitor Reserpine are reported below:

SLC18A2

For this transporter, a known and well described fluorescent surrogate substrate was used: FFN206. A dose-dependent FFN206 fluorescent increase was detected in the SLC18A2 induced condition only, showing EC₅₀ values of ~ 2 μM. Below are reported the dose-response curves of the two blockers tested, TBZ and Reserpine:

SLC13A3

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in Tyrode's buffer Na⁺ free). Succinic acid and α -ketoglutaric acid were used as substrates:

SLC23A1

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). L-Ascorbic Acid was used as substrate. The kinetic traces obtained when cells were pre-incubated with the specific inhibitor Phloretin (300 μ M) are also indicated:

SLC5A11

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). Myo-inositol was used as substrate:

SLC15A2

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in Tyrode's buffer containing MES/HEPES, pH 7.4). Gly-Sar was used as substrate, co-injected with HCl to reach a final pH of 7.4 and 6.8. As shown in the figure below, the best assay window and pharmacology were obtained using a more acidic pH (6.8). D/R of L-Carnosine at pH 6.8 is also reported:

SLC6A6

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). GABA and Taurine were used as substrates:

SLC6A9

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). Glycine was used as substrate. The kinetic traces obtained when cells were pre-incubated with the specific inhibitor ALX5407 (10 μM) are also indicated:

SLC6A12

Read out: **MP dye** (dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer). GABA was used as substrate:

SLC38A9 (Zip8)

HEK293-SLC38A9 cells were seeded at 7000 cells/well in laminin-coated 384 well plates and grown at 37°C, 5% CO₂ overnight. Doxycyclin was then added for further 24h. On the day of the experiment, cells were washed and loaded with the calcium-5 dye following instructions provided by the manufacturer (Molecular Devices).

(A) Post doxycycline induction (24h, 1 µg/ml), SLC38A9 protein expressed in HekR4 cells localizes to the plasma membrane and endoplasmic reticulum (anti-HA-tag Antibody). There is no detectable protein expression in the absence of doxycyclin (not shown) (B) CdCl₂ injection (40 µM) leads to SLC38A9-mediated Cd²⁺ uptake which can be inhibited with a SLC38A9-inhibiting tool compound.

SLC29A1 (ENT1)

HEK293-SLC29A1 and HEK293-mock cells (from Axxam) were seeded at 80.000 cells/well in 96-well E-plates and grown at 37°C, 5% CO₂ for 22 h in an xCELLigence RTCA station. After 22 h, cells were pretreated for 1 h with either vehicle (no inhibitor) or 1 µM NBTI (ENT1 inhibitor) and subsequently stimulated with increasing concentrations of adenosine. NBTI enhanced the potency of adenosine in both SLC29A1 overexpressing and mock cells, indicating ENT1 is endogenously expressed in HEK293 cells and ENT1 inhibition increases extracellular adenosine concentrations. This demonstrated functionality of ENT1 in an impedance-based assay.

SLC6A2 (NET)

HEK293-JumpIn-SLC6A2 were seeded at 60.000 cells/well in 96-well E-plates and grown in the presence (+dox) or absence (-dox) of 1µg/ml doxycycline (dox) at 37°C, 5% CO₂ for 22 h in an xCELLigence RTCA station. After 22 h, cells were pretreated with either vehicle (no inhibitor) or 1 µM nisoxetine (NET inhibitor) and subsequently stimulated with increasing concentrations of either norepinephrine, dopamine, or epinephrine.

Dox-treated cells (expressing NET) attenuated the apparent potency of all three substrates for alpha-2 adrenergic receptors expressed on the HEK293 cells. Nisoxetine rescued the apparent potency of all three substrates in dox-treated cells, with the largest rescue observed using norepinephrine. This indicates NET is functional and removes extracellular substrate.

SLC6A3 (DAT)

HEK293-JumpIn-DAT cells were seeded at 60,000 cells/well in 96-well E-plates and grown in the presence (+dox) or absence (-dox) of 1µg/ml doxycycline (dox) at 37°C, 5% CO₂ for 22 h in an xCELLigence RTCA station. After 22 h, cells were pretreated with either vehicle (no inhibitor), 10µM GBR12909 (atypical DAT inhibitor) or 10µM cocaine (classical DAT inhibitor) and subsequently stimulated with increasing concentrations of dopamine. Dox-treated cells (expressing DAT) attenuated the apparent potency of dopamine for alpha-2 adrenergic receptors expressed on the HEK293 cells. GBR12909 and cocaine rescued the apparent potency of dopamine in dox-treated cells, attaining the largest “assay window” at 10µM dopamine. This indicates DAT is functional and removes extracellular substrate.

SLC1A3 (EAAT1)

HEK293-JumpIn-EAAT1 cells were seeded at 60,000 cells/well in 96-well E-plates and grown in the presence (+dox) or absence (-dox) of 1µg/ml doxycycline (dox) at 37°C, 5% CO₂ for 22 h in an xCELLigence RTCA station. After 22 h, cells were pretreated with either vehicle (no inhibitor) or 10µM TFB-TBOA (competitive

EAAT1 inhibitor) and subsequently stimulated with increasing concentrations of glutamate. Dox-treated cells (expressing DAT) showed a markedly increased impedance response to glutamate, which is likely the result of an intracellular event rather than glutamate receptor activation. TFB-TBOA could completely block any glutamate-induced response, indicating the glutamate responses are EAAT1-mediated.

Discussion

More than 30 cell lines were analysed, using either fluorescent dyes, or the xCELLigence technology. Cells were stimulated with substrates, known from the literature or suggested upon WP2 analysis; when available, SLC inhibitors were also tested for further assay validation.

The goals of Task 3.1 were achieved with no relevant deviation from DoA occurred.

Conclusion

In WP3, Task 3.1:

a) a total of 29 electrogenic SLCs were tested with a Fluorescent Membrane Potential sensitive dye, proving the functionality for 17 of them. Therefore, we can assert that MP dye may represent a useful tool to characterize and validate electrogenic SLCs. Additional tools are represented by ion-specific dyes: an example is the Fluo-8 NW, which could be used to validate SLCs which mediate influx of Calcium ions. The abovementioned read-outs are all eligible for high-throughput screening applications.

Some SLCs were classified as not validated, using, as read-out, the abovementioned fluorescent dyes. These results could be explained by several reasons, such as:

- ❖ No plasma membrane expression of the SLC (e.g.: SLC11A1)
- ❖ Poor functionality of the SLC:
 - Not proved electrogenicity (unknow effective transport reaction stoichiometry)
 - Specific different experimental conditions required: e.g., voltage dependency (e.g., SLC1A6, SLC17A1)
- ❖ Read out specificity (e.g., biosensor>MP)
- ❖ Alternative substrates (for some SLCs a board collection of potential substrates is reported, but not all them were tested)
- ❖ Non-functional SLC (accessory subunit missing ? non-optimal cellular environnement ?)

b) 1 SLC, transporting Zn²⁺, was tested using of fluorescent dye

c) 4 SLCs were tested by using an impedance-based assay, demonstrating the functionality for all of them. The xCELLigence platform has therefore proven helpful for assessing both electrogenic and non-electrogenic SLCs, which share the same substrate with a GPCR, either by using GPCR activation or other substrate-induced responses as a readout.

Repository for primary data

Primary and analysed data are stored in the ReSolute SharePoint in the WP3 folder. As part of the data management plan, we are currently evaluating systematic and sustainable publication procedures for assay protocols and characteristics in public databases like PubChem.